

Application Note

Beyond the Wheatstone bridge: Extend precision by switching

Multiplexed AC resistance measurements

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Obtaining a high precision in resistance measurements is paramount for many tasks related to fundamental science and applications. The Wheatstone bridge is a particularly conducive circuit arrangement for making extremely high-precision measurements because it dilutes the parasitic influences of the instrumentation on the result by several orders of magnitude. We will show which parasitics are and aren't addressed by the Wheatstone bridge, as well as how to improve precision further using multiplexed AC measurements available from modern instruments such as the Tensormeter. Ultimately, we will see that the error mitigation offered by the Tensormeter is so good that the bridge topology itself is no longer necessary in order to obtain 9 or more digits of precision in a conventional 4-wire resistance measurement. We highlight resistor noise index characterization as the most challenging task in terms of precision measurements and show that multiplexed AC measurements are the ultimate approach for this task. Such measurements are easier than previous proposals and allow the total elimination of all $1/f$ noise originating from the measurement device.

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1. Introduction

Precision is a measure for the level of repeatability that one can guarantee when determining a numerical quantity. A large precision for resistance measurements allows recording small relative changes of the value of a resistor for applications such as material science, sensors and metrology. In all of these scenarios, one wishes for the precision to be solely limited by the device-under-test (DUT), and for the instrumentation to have a negligible effect. In practice however, this goal can be extremely hard to achieve and, in particular, the general rise of electronic noise at low frequencies (“ $1/f$ noise”) poses a severe precision limit, because it limits the useful time one can possibly spend averaging a reading to improve its precision.

The most challenging application in terms of detecting small relative changes of resistors is the characterization of the resistor noise index. Resistors with good material quality, such as those used for sensors or in metrology have noise indices of -60 dB or smaller. The quantification of such low noise indices requires the determination of relative resistance changes in the sub-ppb range (i.e. smaller than 1 part in a billion or 10^{-9}). Therefore, resistor noise index measurement shall serve as a paradigmatic example to demonstrate the merits of the Tensormeter for ultra-high precision measurements with and without Wheatstone bridge topologies. Still, the presented methods and concept are important for other high precision measurements, too.

In our preceding Tech Note¹, we have shown that the resistor noise index is an equivalent way of stating the relative precision limit of a resistor – albeit an unwieldy and unintuitive one. In this Application Note, we will usually mention

both the noise index NI and the corresponding unitless relative precision limit σ_{lim} .

As the measurement of the resistor noise index is the ultimate challenge in terms of resistance measurements with high precision, international standards about a suitable approach have been formulated in the 1960ies, namely the MIL-STD 202G Method 308 and the equivalent IEC norm 60195. In brief, the method described therein relies on variable gain amplifiers and matching certain readings manually. Unfortunately, from a 21st century point of view, these methods appear grossly deprecated and should no longer be used to determine noise indices, as they introduce many large error sources. Since the advent of digital signal processing, there are far more stable and better methods to conduct high precision measurements. We will go through some of these contemporarily relevant methods below.

2. Classical Wheatstone bridge

The Wheatstone bridge topology is conventionally used to measure small relative changes of resistance. Instead of a direct 4-wire resistance measurement of the device under test (DUT), the bridge uses two matched pairs of resistors for a total of four resistors, at least one of which is the DUT, as shown in **Figure 1**.

The bridge is supplied with a bridge current I_S that splits almost evenly between both branches of the bridge. The measured differential bridge

Figure 1: Classical Wheatstone resistor bridge configuration (brown) with power source on the left and voltmeter on the right. The differential preamplifier is optional.

¹ “The Resistor Noise Index – an intuitive reformulation”, [Zenodo 10998364](https://zenodo.org/record/10998364), (2023)

voltage V_B allows calculating the bridge resistance as $R_B = V_B/I_S$. Ideally, when the resistors in the bridge are perfectly matched, $R_B = 0$. In practice, a matching ratio R_B/R of 10^{-3} can be routinely achieved with moderate effort. This arrangement suppresses the parasitic properties of the instrumentation mainly in two ways: First, the noise of the power source appears almost entirely as a common signal to both voltage sense nodes, so it is strongly suppressed by the differential voltmeter. Second, the differential signal is very small, ideally only the relative change of the DUT is detected. This allows a large differential input signal gain to be used, which strongly suppresses all subsequent errors and noise sources of the voltmeter.

When one of the four bridge resistors changes by a small amount of ΔR , the bridge resistance R_B will change only by $\Delta R/4$. Still, even for the precision measurement of a single resistor, the advantages of the Wheatstone bridge far outweigh this attenuation of the detectable signal change.

With respect to noise index measurements, one can construct the bridge with four similar DUT resistors. Their individual resistance changes due to current-induced excess noise will be uncorrelated, so while this practice does not quite quadruple the effectively visible current-induced relative change, it still doubles it. In consequence, the Wheatstone bridge method for measurements of current-induced resistor noise will implicitly measure a noise index that is half of (or 6 dB lower than) the actual noise index of a single resistor.

While the Wheatstone bridge helps attenuating various error and noise sources, it doesn't quite compensate them. In the following, we will estimate what kind of precision one could hope to achieve using various types of instrumentation in the context of noise index

measurements with a Wheatstone bridge. We will identify these residual noise sources, show how to mitigate their impact and explain how to realize these approaches using the Tensormeter.

3. Offset and Reference errors

The current-induced resistor noise has a $1/f$ power spectral shape, which means that it is a low frequency effect that particularly matters when considering long measurement time scales. As a result, the suppression of low frequency noise and drift originating from the instrumentation is absolutely paramount.

One important source of $1/f$ noise from the instrumentation is the instability of the signal offset that affects both the current source and the voltmeter. These effects can be very large, which is why many precision measurement devices already implement mitigation strategies. For example, zero-drift (chopper stabilized) sense amplifiers virtually eliminate drift and $1/f$ noise from the differential amplifier. Even better performance is obtained by using alternating current (AC): Modulate the power source and demodulate the voltage signal for a resistance measurement signal that is independent from the offset and its drift of both the sense and driver amplifiers. This method also eliminates the contribution of thermal voltages which can spontaneously develop between the probing leads.

Therefore, a decent measurement of the resistor noise index should at least use AC to exclude the most important sources of instrumentation-related $1/f$ noise and drift. There are several ways to implement this, e.g. by using lock-in amplifiers or by using a synchronized current source and voltmeter (like Keithley's "Delta Mode"). The Tensormeter can mimic both of these approaches. It can apply sinusoidal AC excitation and demodulation like a lock-in amplifier or it can reverse the drive signal in synchronization with its readout.

A second important source of $1/f$ noise from the instrumentation as shown in **Figure 1** comes from using two separate devices as the power source and voltmeter (e.g. a constant current source and nanovoltmeter). As a result, the sense and driver sides of the experiment will each use a separate voltage reference. Since voltage references, too, exhibit $1/f$ noise, the instantaneous disagreement of the two voltage references will translate to apparent $1/f$ noise of the measured bridge resistance R_B . Although this contribution is suppressed by the matching ratio of the bridge R_B/R , it can still become important for very low noise indices. For two voltage references with a $1/f$ noise limited precision of 0.5 ppm, the relative precision limit for R_B is $\sigma_{lim}(R_B) = \sqrt{2} \cdot 0.5 \cdot 10^{-6} = 7.07 \cdot 10^{-7}$. To obtain the relative precision limit for the DUT resistor, one has to multiply with the bridge matching ratio (we assume $R_B/R = 10^{-3}$) and consider that the Wheatstone bridge attenuates the observable noise by a factor of two when using four DUT resistors:

$$\sigma_{lim}(R) = \frac{R_B}{R} \cdot 2 \cdot \sigma_{lim}(R_B) \quad \mathbf{1}$$

Therefore, for the hypothetical combination of a good current source and good voltmeter in combination with a Wheatstone bridge (**Figure 1**), and while performing an AC experiment to reject the offset errors, the relative precision limit for R can be estimated as $\sigma_{lim}(R) = 1.4 \cdot 10^{-9}$, which corresponds to a noise index of -55 dB.

This figure is inadequate for the characterization of very low noise resistors. One might be able to push the envelope somewhat with even better resistor matching, but there is an easier way to greatly extend the measurable precision limit. **Figure 2** shows how the reference noise contribution can be mitigated entirely, namely

by using an ohmmeter type measurement device instead, i.e. a single device that uses a single internal voltage reference to derive its drive signal from and to trace its sense signal to.

This is also one of the most commonly used approaches for noise index measurements nowadays². Instead of an ohmmeter, one can also employ a multichannel lock-in amplifier that allows monitoring both the drive voltage and sense voltage amplitudes in the scale of a common voltage reference. Likewise, the Tensormeter uses a common voltage reference for all its signals.

Figure 2: Wheatstone bridge (brown) driven from and measured by a single ohmmeter instead of a separate power source and a voltmeter.

The rejection of the reference-related $1/f$ noise for resistance measurements works in the same way for all of these devices: If the reference drifts up slightly, there will be commensurate changes in the output current and the sensed voltage, so when the slightly increased sensed voltage is compared to the slightly increased reference voltage, no change is detected.

In order to estimate the relative precision limit for the ohmmeter approach, we have to consider the most influential remaining internal source of $1/f$ noise, namely the gain noise and drift. Measurement devices use high quality resistors internally to convert the voltage reference into a drive signal and to scale the sense signal back into the domain of the voltage reference. These resistors have their own noise

² "Review on excess noise measurements of resistors", *Sensors* 23(3), 1107, (2023) and references therein, by D. Walter, A. Bülow and A. Zimmermann

indices and drifts. For a very high-end multichannel multimeter the noise indices of the gain setting network might compound to an effective gain precision of $\sigma_{\text{lim}}(R_B) = 7.6 \cdot 10^{-9}$ (equivalent to -40 dB). When adopted to our Wheatstone bridge with 10^{-3} -matching and taking into account the factor-of-two penalty of the Wheatstone bridge (Eq. 1), one could determine DUT noise indices down to -94 dB or $1.5 \cdot 10^{-11}$. A highly impressive figure on paper, but it requires the entire measurement device to be kept at a perfectly stable temperature for the duration of the measurement. Even when assuming that the temperature of the measurement device were to be stabilized to better than 0.5 K and the device itself was extraordinarily gain stable at 0.5 ppm/K, the remaining realistic gain change window of 0.25 ppm would collapse the precision limit (via Eq. 1) figure to $5 \cdot 10^{-10}$ or -64 dB. So while a good ohmmeter might do better than separate current sources and voltmeters, its performance hinges strongly on how well its gain stability can be guaranteed.

4. Ratiometric AC measurements

The previous sections left a somewhat sobering outlook. There appear to be several parasitic factors that suddenly become very tough to overcome when targeting a precision of better than approximately 10^{-9} or resistor noise indices well below -60 dB. Even premium-class devices suffer from seemingly inevitable limitations, even when already factoring in the precision benefits of using a Wheatstone bridge configuration. Improving the matching ratio of the bridge can work but it is a rather cumbersome and highly situational solution.

Using the Tensormeter, one has access to a number of additional measurement approaches due to its integrated switch matrix. This allows an even more complete elimination of $1/f$ noise sources of the instrument.

Figure 3: Wheatstone bridge (brown) measurement is interleaved with a reference resistor string (blue) measurement.

The first of these approaches is shown in **Figure 3**, where a second Wheatstone bridge, or rather a dummy thereof, is shown in blue. The dummy is constructed such, that the measured resistance will be again on the order of R_B and the load seen by the driver is R , in order to keep the operation point of the measurement device as seamless as possible when the two bridges are measured in an interleaved way. Importantly, the middle dummy resistor R_B must have a very low noise index and must have low drift over time or temperature so it can be used as a reference. This is much easier to achieve in practice, however, than the sub-K level temperature stabilization of an entire measurement device.

The measurement proceeds as follows: An AC resistance measurement is made for the DUT bridge to obtain its bridge resistance value. Next, the switches connect the dummy instead of the DUT bridge and an AC resistance measurement is made to obtain the middle dummy resistor value. These two measurements are constantly done in turn. As each individual measurement is carried out using the AC ohmmeter approach, there will be no offset or reference errors and the dominant error will be $1/f$ noise and drift due to gain instability. However, as the exact same electronics are used to perform both measurements, the instantaneous error will be the same for both measurements and the ratio between both measurements will not depend on the ohmmeter's $1/f$ noise at all. The switching

frequency sets an upper frequency limit up to which the drift and $1/f$ noise are compensated, which is why it is important to switch at a frequency of at least a few Hz typically.

Using this approach, the attainable precision is now only limited by the stability and $1/f$ noise of the Wheatstone bridge dummy, with the dominant contribution stemming from the middle dummy resistor. If we consider a large wire-wound resistor with a noise index of -80 dB and again a 10^{-3} matching in the brown DUT bridge, the lower bound for the measurable DUT noise index (Eq. 1) turns out to be $1.5 \cdot 10^{-13}$ or -134 dB. It is also important to note that the measurement device need not be thermally stabilized to obtain this capability from the Tensormeter.

This number is so fantastical that it requires some parsing. First, the amount of integration time necessary to push the thermal noise contribution low enough to reach this precision floor would be weeks even with the most aggressive high-current drive. Second, the reference resistor would have to be kept itself constant at a sub-ppb level, which is unreasonable even with perfect thermal stabilization due to aging. In light of these additional restrictions that lie beyond the scope of the measurement device, resistance metrology experiments achieve precisions on the order of 10^{-10} , limited primarily by drift. That implies that the approach shown in **Figure 3** is “too good” in terms of $1/f$ noise rejection and that one could get away with something simpler.

5. Removing the Wheatstone bridge

One of the main reasons for originally implementing a Wheatstone bridge in precision measurements has been its ability to strongly suppress noise from the driver. When one is interested in the base precision, the important noise contribution is $1/f$ noise. But as we have learnt in the previous section, it is possible to

suppress the dominant $1/f$ noise contributions with the Tensormeter irrespective of what the DUT actually is. Using AC drive removes the influence of the offset $1/f$ noise and doing a ratiometric measurement with a reference removes the gain $1/f$ noise. As a result, there is not much $1/f$ noise left for the Wheatstone bridge to suppress and it is worth to consider what level of precision could be achieved with the Tensormeter without Wheatstone bridges, i.e. in a simple ratiometric AC 4-wire resistance measurement.

To this end, **Figure 4** shows a very simple measurement scheme that can be set up directly with the Tensormeter. It consists of no bridges and merely two resistors that need not even be closely matched (same order of magnitude is perfectly sufficient). Both resistors are measured in turn and can be expressed as a ratio of one another.

Figure 4: The Wheatstone bridge (brown) and reference resistor string (blue) are both reduced to a single resistor each.

Like before, one can use one DUT resistor and one ultra-low noise reference resistor. In this case, as the reference is assumed to be stable, any measured signal or $1/f$ noise corresponds directly to that of the DUT resistor and the lowest noise index that can be determined in this manner is bounded by the noise index and stability of the reference resistor. Using a good reference resistor and basic passive thermal stabilization, ppb-level precision is attainable with little effort. For comparison: top-end multimeters struggle to offer better than 100 ppb precision when one takes the Wheatstone bridge away.

Another strong advantage of this topology is that large signal changes can be measured without loss in precision or linearity, making it a good candidate for sensors or careful experiments in physics and material sciences. One could easily change the DUT resistance by several 10 % and observe a commensurate change in the ratiometric reading.

Still, one should not forget that the Wheatstone bridge has another advantage as mentioned in the introduction: It makes the differential sense signal small, so one can use a small measurement range with better white noise performance, allowing to reach the base precision faster. Therefore, when the complexity and severely restricted measurement range of the Wheatstone bridge do not matter, the configuration shown in **Figure 3** is still preferable over the simple ratiometric 4-wire resistance measurement.

6. Total $1/f$ noise mitigation

The previous two topologies explained in **Figure 3** and **Figure 4** made use of a reference resistor in order to eliminate the gain $1/f$ noise of the Tensormeter and replace it with the $1/f$ noise of the reference resistor instead. This enables extreme levels of $1/f$ noise limited precision, even better than can be realistically achieved in light of inevitable amounts of drift or aging of the reference resistor.

For the particular task of noise index characterization, there is yet another strategy, which fundamentally allows to characterize arbitrarily low noise indices and, at the same time, does away with the requirement for an ultra-low noise reference resistor. Using the topology in **Figure 4** as an example, one can use two similar DUT resistors instead of a DUT and a reference resistor. That way, the measured noise of the resistor ratio would be factor of $\sqrt{2}$ times (or 3 dB) larger than the relative current-induced resistor noise of a single DUT resistor.

Interestingly, the precision of this method is bounded only by the matching stability of the two resistors. If one keeps both devices tightly thermally coupled, or better yet, both stabilized, one can measure very low noise indices.

Figure 5: Resistance ratio noise spectral density of two similar resistors measured in a ratiometric AC 4-wire measurement using Tensormeter RTM2. The $1/f$ contribution is indicated in brown.

An example is shown in **Figure 5**: The resistance ratio of two similar low-noise resistors reveals a low frequency $1/f$ contribution. For these particular 1 k Ω resistors, the ratio spectrum has a $1/\sqrt{f}$ slope coefficient of $4 \cdot 10^{-9}$ (intersection of the brown line with $f = 1$ Hz). In order to obtain the noise index of the resistors, we can convert this spectral coefficient into a noise index figure as explained in our Tech Note¹, taking into account that the measurement enhances the noise by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$. The result is a noise index of -47 dB (the manufacturer specifies an upper bound of -40 dB).

The same approach generalizes to the Wheatstone bridge topology shown in **Figure 3**. By using two similar DUT bridges made of 8 DUT resistors and no reference resistor, one can combine the advantage of total $1/f$ noise rejection offered by the ratiometric measurement with the improved white noise of the Wheatstone bridge. In order to calculate the relative precision limit for one of the individual 8 resistors, one cannot assume that the matching

ratios of both bridges be similar. In detail, there will be two different bridge resistances, R_{B1} and R_{B2} , and the ratiometric measurement will measure the ratio of these bridge resistances $r = R_{B1}/R_{B2}$. The measured relative precision limit of the ratio $\sigma_{lim}(r)$ has to be scaled by some factors that depend on both bridges' matching:

$$\sigma_{lim}(R) = \frac{R_{B2}}{R} \cdot \frac{2}{\sqrt{1+r^2}} \cdot \sigma_{lim}(r) \quad \mathbf{2}$$

As with the ratiometric 4-wire approach, the ratiometric Wheatstone approach has no fundamental lower limit of noise indices that can be characterized. Therefore, the important metric becomes the time spent in order to resolve a certain noise index. As an example, we consider 8 ultra-low noise resistors with a noise index of -80 dB, i.e. $\sigma_{lim}(R) = 7.6 \cdot 10^{-11}$. If we assume matching ratios on the order of 10^{-3} for both bridges and a ratio between the bridges on the order of $|r| \approx 1$, the observable relative precision floor of the ratiometric reading will be a rather large $\sigma_{lim}(r) \approx 5 \cdot 10^{-8}$. Such precision can typically be reached within several seconds of measurement time, which greatly alleviates the effort for thermal stabilization of the DUT resistors. This method is so fast, simple and void of potential error sources, that we propose it as a routine manufacturer investigation for low noise resistor datasheets.

7. Summary

When the resistance of a device-under-test is to be measured at ppb-level precision, as is necessary e.g. for noise index characterization, the Wheatstone bridge has become an absolute necessity. It effectively extends the instrument's precision floor (on the order of 100 ppb even for high-end instruments) at the cost of range, linearity, and some complexity.

Ratiometric AC resistance measurements offered by the Tensorometer eviscerate the $1/f$ noise limitations that preclude traditional

instruments from reaching ppb-level precision in simple 4-wire measurements. We demonstrate this capability by measuring a resistor noise index of -47 dB (3.5 ppb) without employing a Wheatstone bridge. At the same time, the range and linearity remain unaffected.

Precision measurements should thus make use of three common techniques, all of which are almost unconditionally favorable. Namely:

1. An AC drive allows to reject the $1/f$ noise associated with signal offsets in the entire signal chain.
2. Using an instrument with a common voltage reference for both the drive and sense signals rejects the noise influence of the voltage reference.
3. Interleaving the DUT measurement with a reference resistor measurement rejects the $1/f$ noise related to the gain instability of the instrument.

Wheatstone bridges can still be used in addition, whenever the goal of the measurement is to obtain high precision in the shortest possible amount of time and the signal range is small, e.g. for resistor noise index characterization.

The merit of ratiometric AC resistance measurements with the Tensorometer for the purpose of resistor noise index characterization is particularly striking: It removes instrument limitations entirely. Even ultra-low noise indices on the order of -80 dB and below become easily measurable.

To this end, we suggest that ratiometric AC resistance measurements become an industry standard for the $1/f$ (excess) noise specification of resistive sensors and low noise resistors. Manufacturers of such components can implement this reliable, easy and fast routine measurement into their characterization protocol, helping them to better specify and endorse their products.